

Quantifier spreading errors during pronoun processing in aphasia

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Quantifier spreading refers to a difficulty interpreting quantifier scope during sentence comprehension (Brooks & Parshina, 2019). Although this phenomenon has often been observed in language acquisition studies (O'Grady, Suzuki, & Yoshinaga, 2010; Sekerina & Sauermaun, 2015), there is evidence that persons with aphasia (PWA) may as well be prone to quantifier spreading errors (Grodzinsky, Wexler, Chien, Marakovitz, & Solomon, 1993; Philip & Avrutin, 1998; Roca Hoogsteder, 2012). The current study examined sentence comprehension of quantified and non-quantified subjects in Turkish persons with non-fluent aphasia (PWA) using a truth-value judgement tasks in a sentence-picture matching paradigm. A total number of 12 PWA were recruited (8 females, *Age* = 59.7, *SD* = 14.55) who were asked to listen to 24 sentences in two conditions of non-quantified (1) and quantified subject noun phrases (2). In sentence materials, different anaphoric variables in object positions were controlled for (pronoun, reflexive¹, and R-expression). The task was to decide if the visual depiction presented to the participants correctly described the sentence content. Half of the sentences were correctly depicted in visual images while the other half contained a misinterpreted depiction of the propositional content of sentences (see Figure 1).

- (1) Tavşan kendini / onu / maymunu gösteriyor.
Rabbit itself / it / monkey SHOWS.PRESPROG.3SG
'The rabbit is pointing at itself /it /the monkey'
- (2) Her tavşan kendini / onu / maymunu gösteriyor.
Every rabbit itself / it / monkey SHOWS.PRESPROG.3SG
'Every rabbit is pointing at itself /it /the monkey'

Figure 1. An example visual depiction for incorrect (A) and correct (B) interpretations for the quantified pronoun sentence 'Every rabbit is pointing at the monkey?'

¹ Please note that in Turkish there are two forms of anaphoric elements which function as reflexive (i.e. 'kendi' and 'kendisi'), according to some accounts, the latter behaves as a long-distance reflexive and it can refer to non-local antecedents (see e.g. Kornfilt, 2001). We only included the default 'kendi' reflexive in this study.

A set of mixed-effects regression models have shown that the PWA responded equally accurately to sentences with and without quantified subjects overall ($\beta = -0.33$, $SE = 0.29$, $z = -1.12$, $p = 0.26$), however, there were significant effects of Mismatch ($\beta = -1.22$, $SE = 0.47$, $z = -2.55$, $p = 0.01$) and an interaction between Mismatch and Quantifier conditions ($\beta = -1.41$, $SE = 0.68$, $z = -2.05$, $p = 0.04$). This indicates that PWA had difficulty judging the truth value in sentences with a mismatching visual depiction, and this difficulty was greater in sentences with quantified subjects (See Figure 2). Therefore, we confirm that the Turkish PWA were susceptible to quantifier spreading errors. Furthermore, the PWA had an increased difficulty in interpreting sentences with R-expressions in comparison to both reflexives ($\beta = 0.93$, $SE = 0.31$, $z = 2.99$, $p = 0.007$) and pronouns ($\beta = 0.83$, $SE = 0.31$, $z = 2.70$, $p = 0.01$), there were no differences between pronoun and reflexive variables, however. It seems to us that our findings are best accounted for by hypotheses on impaired lexical-semantic processing (see e.g. Choy & Thompson, 2010). However, at this stage we cannot rule out the possibility that reduced visual attention in aphasia may have led to greater amount of misinterpretations.

Figure 2. The PWA's mean accuracy of responses to different variables (left), and to quantified and non-quantified subject pronouns (right).

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